

Unfreezing the past: near Pan-Svalbard assessment of cryospheric hazards to Arctic cultural heritage

Ionut Cristi Nicu^{a,*}, Paloma Guzman^b, Cristian Constantin Stoleriu^c

^a High North Department, Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research (NIKU), Fram Centre, N-9296, Tromsø, Norway

^b Digital Archaeology Department, Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research (NIKU), Storgata 2, 0155, Oslo, Norway

^c Department of Geography, Faculty of Geography and Geology, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, 700505, Iasi, Romania

HIGHLIGHTS

- The first cryospheric hazards assessment of Arctic cultural heritage on a regional scale
- Nordenskiöld Land has been identified as a hotspot for both RTS and TEG threats to cultural heritage.
- Adaptive management is urgently needed to mitigate climate-driven heritage loss in Svalbard.
- The study provides a scalable model for Arctic cultural heritage hazard assessment.

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Retrogressive thaw slumps (RTS)
Thermo-erosion gully (TEG)
Svalbard
Permafrost degradation
Cultural heritage
Hazard assessment

ABSTRACT

Permafrost degradation is accelerating across the Arctic, posing growing risks to cultural heritage (CH) sites. This study presents the first archipelago-scale hazard assessment of CH to retrogressive thaw slumps (RTS) and thermo-erosion gullies (TEG) in Svalbard, one of the fastest-warming regions globally. By overlaying recent RTS and TEG inventories with the spatial distribution of protected CH sites, we quantify hazard exposure for 55.3 % of all CH sites, 50.8 % of safety zones, and 50 % of priority sites, with a focus on central and southern Spitsbergen. Nordenskiöld Land has been identified as the primary high-risk area for RTS impacts, with direct threats to CH sites. Wedel Jarlsberg Land and James I Land rank as secondary and tertiary risk regions. Safety zones face the highest RTS risk in Wedel Jarlsberg Land, while priority sites are most at risk in Nordenskiöld Land. The latter region also dominates TEG-related risks and accounts for the majority of direct and buffer zone overlaps due to its high density of both hazards and CH sites and permafrost hazards. Wedel Jarlsberg Land has been identified as a secondary TEG hotspot. Risk increases substantially with buffer distance, underscoring the potential for future hazard expansion. The results highlight the need for regionally targeted, risk-informed conservation strategies that integrate climate hazard data into heritage management, monitoring, and spatial planning. The study also demonstrates the value of the *SvalCryo* dataset as a tool for supporting adaptive governance and contributing to broader climate adaptation and non-economic loss tracking frameworks across the Arctic.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is currently experiencing accelerated environmental transformations driven by climate change, with permafrost degradation emerging as a key factor destabilising landscapes (Rantanen et al., 2022). In permafrost-dominated regions, retrogressive thaw slumps (RTS) and thermo-erosion gullies (TEG) are among the most prominent cryospheric hazards (Liu et al., 2024; Nicu et al., 2024; Rubensdotter et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2025).

RTS are characterized by ground collapse resulting from thawing of ice-rich permafrost, causing sediment displacement. The typical RTS morphology features a bimodal shape with steep backwall, a low-angle bottom (sliding surface), and a tongue of displaced saturated soil that undergoes reworking during movement. Since these deposits usually occur near fluvial channels or coastline, they are rapidly transported, leaving a relatively permanent slump scar on the landscape. Vertical back-scarps become unstable to gravitation once active layers develop, likely triggering further processes in coming years (Nesterova et al.,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ionut.cristi.nicu@niku.no (I.C. Nicu).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.180424>

Received 21 May 2025; Received in revised form 2 September 2025; Accepted 3 September 2025

Available online 5 September 2025

0048-9697/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2024; Nicu et al., 2021).

TEG develop due to combined fluvial and thermal erosion along ice wedges or frost cracks. Their initiation can be triggered by heat transfer from small water tracks that penetrate the surrounding soils, deepening the active layer locally. Extended or warmer melt seasons cause deeper thawing of ice-rich sediments, oversaturating soils and enhancing erosion. These processes significantly alter landscapes, and pose risks to infrastructure (Hjort et al., 2022), ecosystems (Chen et al., 2023), and CH (Nicu and Fatorić, 2023). While hazards assessments related to landslides (Bonini et al., 2023; Jiao et al., 2019; Kim and Kim, 2021; Nicu and Asăndulesei, 2018; Sdao et al., 2013) and gully erosion to CH sites are well documented globally (Nicu, 2021; Pederson et al., 2006; Santos et al., 2023), their high-latitude counterparts remain underexplored. These hazards are intensifying as global temperatures rise. Svalbard, a high-Arctic Archipelago, is especially vulnerable to permafrost degradation, with a warming rate four times faster than the global average (Dahlke et al., 2020).

Unlike many inhabited or architecturally preserved sites elsewhere, Svalbard's CH is primarily composed of surface-level remains, such as whaling stations, trapping cabins, mining relics, and scientific installations, distributed across remote and environmentally exposed landscapes. These features are not only vulnerable to extreme climate processes but are also subject to minimal active conservation. The adaptability of humans to Arctic extremes is reflected in this CH, which (Gerlach and Kinossian, 2016) term 'haunted landscape', a setting where projecting power through presence of the past are not only visible but actively shape present-day perceptions and identities. For instance, Barentsburg, Soviet-era monuments, slogans (e.g., "Our goal—communism!") and architecture "haunt" the town as ghostly reminders of a bygone ideological project, evoking nostalgia, power, and contested histories.

Svalbard's CH is legally protected under the Environmental Protection Act, which mandates the preservation of all human traces dating from before 1946. This broad legislative scope reflects the symbolic and geopolitical role of CH in Arctic governance (Iversen, 2023). However, climate change has intensified the vulnerability of Svalbard's CH by accelerating permafrost thaw and increasing the frequency and magnitude of cryospheric hazards such as RTS (Nicu et al., 2023; Nicu et al., 2021) and TEG (Nicu et al., 2022; Rubensdotter et al., 2025). Simultaneously, anthropogenic pressures, particularly the rise in sea-based tourism (such as cruise ships and private vessels), maritime traffic, and coastal landings, are exacerbating risks to cultural heritage, especially in accessible coastal areas (Tømmervik et al., 2025).

The intersection of these processes exposes key governance gaps, including the lack of criteria to distinguish between heritage sites requiring active versus passive protection, and the absence of systematic protocols for managing inevitable losses through documentation, relocation, or emergency excavation (Security, 2024). Moreover, these challenges highlight the limitations of a deterministic legislative model that offers uniform protection without differentiation or prioritisation. There is a pressing need for tools to aid management agencies in strategically identifying vulnerable heritage sites, prioritising interventions, and guiding the development of climate-adaptive heritage inventories across the Arctic. Beyond informing local conservation efforts, spatial hazard data can contribute to global climate governance agendas. In particular, this work supports emerging efforts to integrate cultural heritage into climate change monitoring frameworks and the Loss and Damage (L&D) agenda, where non-economic losses—including cultural, symbolic, and territorial degradation—remain critically underrepresented (Ford et al., 2025).

Currently, a systematic hazard assessment of RTS and TEG impacts on CH sites at the archipelago scale is lacking. The recently published *SvalCryo* inventory (Nicu et al., 2024) provides near pan-Svalbard mapping of these processes, documenting 3679 RTS and 4812 TEG across 14 ice-free regions, covering over half of Svalbard's surface. This dataset offers a unique opportunity to quantitatively assess the hazard

exposure of 4590 sites identified as CH (Riksantikvaren).

This study presents the first comprehensive, archipelago-wide hazard assessment of CH sites in Svalbard by overlaying the spatial distribution of RTS and TEG with that of protected CH assets. Quantifying the extent and nature of RTS and TEG exposure provides critical insights for risk-informed conservation planning in a rapidly changing Arctic. In doing so, the analysis contributes to the growing literature on climate impacts on Arctic CH and offers a scalable approach for integrating spatial hazard datasets into CH management and climate adaptation tracking frameworks (Biesbroek et al., 2025).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data

2.1.1. Cryospheric hazards (RTS and TEG)

In this study, the *SvalCryo* inventory of RTS and TEG published by (Nicu et al., 2024) was used as a base. The inventory covers 14 of the 28 regions of Svalbard Archipelago, namely Andreé Land, Dickson Land, James I Land, Nordenskiöld Land, Bünsow Land, Olav V Land, Sabine Land, Nathorst Land, Heer Land, Wedel Jarlsberg Land, Torell Land, Sørkapp Land, Barentsøya and Edgeøya. This represents a very large part of the ice-free area of the archipelago.

2.1.2. Svalbard cultural heritage dataset and management

The cultural heritage dataset is freely available from the Norwegian Directorate for Cultural Heritage (Riksantikvaren). Within this dataset, there are three main categories: *CH sites* (comprising 4590 sites) – representing physical cultural heritage elements with defined geographical boundaries and object-specific information; *safety zones* (1987 areas) – are designed protective perimeters around automatically protected heritage sites intended to mitigate impacts from nearby activities (natural or anthropogenic), making them critical for conservation planning; *priority sites* (99 sites) – are designated for urgent preservation due to their vulnerability to environmental threats (e.g., permafrost thaw) and anthropogenic activity (e.g., trampling, disturbing structures, moving/removing or adding objects, wear and tear) have been identified as exacerbating factors (Tømmervik et al., 2025). The boundaries for priority sites have been delineated, yet according to the Svalbard Management Plan, these are regarded as advisory and may be subject to adjustment in complex environments. The descriptions were summarised and can be found in Table 1.

The Svalbard Environmental Protection Act entrusts the Governor of Svalbard and the Directorate for Cultural Heritage as the entities responsible for the preservation of cultural environments. However, the effective implementation of climate adaptation strategies remains a significant governance challenge. The management plan for 2013–2023 proposed concrete measures to address climate risks at prioritised heritage sites—approximately 100 in total (99 left today), with 50 deemed of especially high priority. These range from monitoring and documentation to temporary stabilisation and, in some cases, emergency excavations or relocations. Nevertheless, the selection process for determining which sites to actively preserve and which to allow to deteriorate still lacks a fully transparent framework. Furthermore, the degree of intervention varies significantly, and long-term strategies are contingent on research and monitoring programmes that have yet to be fully institutionalized. The absence of an integrated system to translate site-level data into adaptive governance has the effect of limiting the capacity to proactively manage risks, particularly as permafrost thaw and coastal erosion intensify.

2.2. RTS HRR variability across various permafrost zones

RTS headwall retreat rates (HRR) in Svalbard should be contextualised within the broader Arctic variability observed in ice-rich permafrost zones. Although direct measurements from Svalbard are

Table 1
Summarised description of the three categories of CH on Svalbard.

Category	No. of sites/ Areas	Main Characteristics	Types of Threats	Management/ Legal Considerations
CH sites	4590	Physical cultural heritage elements with defined boundaries and detailed object-specific info	Environmental (permafrost thaw, erosion), anthropogenic (tourism, disturbance)	Automatically protected; subject to preservation under Svalbard Environmental Protection Act; dataset freely available from the Directorate for Cultural Heritage
Safety zones	1987	Protective perimeters around automatically protected sites to mitigate impacts from surrounding activities	Natural (landscape changes, erosion), anthropogenic (development, recreational use)	Critical for conservation planning; buffers mitigate direct and indirect impacts; governed by management plans and legal frameworks
Priority sites	99	Sites designated for urgent preservation due to high vulnerability to environmental and human threats	Permafrost thaw, trampling, structural disturbance, tourism-driven wear and tear	Advisory mapped boundaries; concrete measures include monitoring, stabilisation, and emergency actions; governance challenge due to lack of integrated adaptive management systems

limited, comparative data and geomorphological analogues demonstrate the following HRR: 6.3 m yr⁻¹ in the Russian High Arctic (Barth et al., 2025), 6.2 m yr⁻¹ in the Canadian High Arctic (Eureka Sound Lowlands, Ellesmere and Axel Heiberg Islands) (Ward Jones et al., 2019), 2.4–3.2 m yr⁻¹ in the Hoh Xil region of the QTP (Luo et al., 2024), 12.4 ± 7.4 m yr⁻¹ on the Peel Plateau and Richardson Mountains of northwestern Canada (Lacelle et al., 2015), Batagay megaslump with 15 m yr⁻¹ (Kizyakov et al., 2023). Therefore, ≥ 6 m yr⁻¹ is regarded as suitable for conservative hazard assessment. The ice-rich sediments and steep slopes of Svalbard align closely with Canadian/Russian High Arctic, where retreat rates are notably higher. The accelerated degradation of permafrost in this region exceeds the global Arctic average, thereby fostering the initiation and growth of RTS (Nicu et al., 2021; Rubensdotter et al., 2025). Furthermore, the severity of RTSs in the cold permafrost of the Bank Islands was found to exceed that observed in the warm permafrost of the QTP. This phenomenon can be attributed to the faster rate of warming experienced by the colder permafrost sites. In the long term, RTS in (especially) Arctic Svalbard, with their higher temperature sensitivity, may pose a significant threat to CH sites (Liu et al., 2024). The use of ≥ 6 m yr⁻¹ captures the median-to-worst-case scenarios observed in analogous regions, which is critical for safeguarding CH sites within 100 m of RTS zones. Subsequently to this value, the next value used (buffer) is 12 m yr⁻¹. Slope aspect and ground ice content are important modifiers: south-facing slopes and ice-rich transition layers can exceed 10 m yr⁻¹ (Nesterova et al., 2024). For CH conservation strategies, this range considers the increased climate sensitivity of Svalbard, whilst acknowledging the possibility of underestimation without localised multi-year monitoring.

2.3. TEG erosion rates variability across various permafrost zones

Same as RTS, TEG erosion rates/advancement rates in Svalbard must be contextualised within the broader variability of the Arctic. The data on various erosion rates from different permafrost zones indicates the following average rates (here, the focus is on the main axis length and not the eroded area): 15.5 m yr⁻¹ on Bylot Island in Canada (Fortier et al., 2007), 23 m yr⁻¹ for a gully on the same Bylot Island (Godin et al., 2012). In general terms, the erosion rates tend to be higher during the first decade following the initiation, before decreasing thereafter. Based on these values and considering the uncertainties of Arctic climate variability, using an erosion rate (buffer) of 20 m for TEG hazard assessment for Svalbard's CH would be representative and reasonable. This is to be followed by a buffer of 30 m.

2.4. Analysis

For the hazard assessment analysis, in addition to the three categories that have previously been mentioned in Section 2.1.2, another category was incorporated. This comprised a 100 m buffer area around CH sites, designated as CH sites 100 m buffer. This was made according to the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act, which explicitly stipulates that all remains from prior to 1946 are automatically protected. Furthermore, all traces of bones and bone fragments discovered on or beneath the ground's surface, along with any indications of human graves, including crosses and other grave markers, are automatically protected irrespective of their age. The protected cultural heritage sites have a 100 m buffer of protected area, the importance of which is equal to that of the site itself. For each of the CH features, represented by a polygon, a buffer was created using the Buffer Tool from ArcGIS Pro. For RTS (6 and 12 m) and TEG (20 and 30 m), the buffers were made around the features from the SvalCryo database.

To make the hazard assessment of CH sites from RTS and TEG, the Intersect Tool from ArcGIS Pro was used. The polygons of RTS and TEG, along with their buffers, were used as base to intersect the four elements of CH: CH sites, CH sites 100 m buffer, safety zones, and priority sites. The methodological flowchart is highlighted in Fig. 1.

3. Results

3.1. CH analysis

At Archipelago scale (Fig. 1), Nordenskiöld Land (no. 5) contains the largest number of CH sites, safety zones and priority sites with 1407, 327, and 14 respectively. This is followed by Albert I Land with 945, 303, and 11 respectively. Oscar II Land comes third highest with 371, 191, and 4 respectively. These regions are followed by regions with moderate concentrations, such as Edgeøya (308, 190, and 8 respectively), Dickson Land (216, 135, and 6 respectively), Prins Karls Forland (199, 151, and no priority sites), Wedel Jarlsberg Land (208, 102, and 5 respectively). And regions with lower concentration of sites, such as Sørkapp Land, Bjørnøya, etc.

Regions such as Albert I Land and Oscar II Land contain dense clusters of 17th–19th century whaling stations and early 20th century mining infrastructure. Their spatial concentration reflects Svalbard's role in Arctic resource exploitation and enhances their collective heritage value (Thuestad et al., 2015).

The numbered regions in green in Fig. 2 correspond to the regions analysed in this study. As can be seen, the present study encompasses more than half of Svalbard's CH sites (55.3%), safety zones (50.8%), and priority sites (50%). The regions analysed are mainly located in the central and southern regions of Spitsbergen, the main island of the archipelago. The inclusion of Nordenskiöld Land, a region characterized by a high density of sites, safety zones and priority sites underscore the study's relevance and significance at both the Archipelago and pan-Arctic scales.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the methodology employed in the study.

3.2. CH hazard assessment to RTS

Several CH hazard assessments for landslides have been carried out in different regions of the world (Bonini et al., 2023). The way in which a classic landslide affects the integrity of CH sites has also been highlighted. However, for their high-latitude counterparts – RTS, the mechanisms are similar but different. An RTS can undermine and bury archaeological layers (stratigraphy), destroying structural remains (e.g. wooden and metal structures, bones), and making it harder or impossible to date or interpret artifacts accurately (Hollesen et al., 2016). Slumping exposes previously frozen artifacts to oxidation, microbial activity and mechanical weathering. Newly exposed organic materials, such as bones, are scavenged by polar bears and Arctic foxes (Flyen and Thuestad, 2023). Meltwater and thawed sediments flow downslope, burying and/or washing away surface artifacts. Uneven thawing along the slump scars causes foundations and Soviet-era buildings from Barentsburg and Pyramiden to crack or tilt. Slump floors often become waterlogged, submerging artifacts. Also, RTS make sites harder (or dangerous) to reach for researchers and site managers. Previous focused research from Greenland (Walls et al., 2020) and Svalbard (Nicu et al., 2021) highlights the suddenness and danger of periglacial landscape degradation to CH in the cold regions of the globe.

To ascertain the number of CH sites that overlap an RTS (Fig. 3, upper image), a comprehensive analysis was conducted. The analysis revealed a total of 11 sites, with 10 of these located in Nordenskiöld Land and one in James I Land. For the 6 m and 12 m buffers around the RTS, the number of sites rises to 15 and 25, respectively. Of these 15 sites, 11 are

located in Nordenskiöld Land, two in Wedel Jarlsberg Land, one in James I Land, and one in Dickson Land. Of the 25 sites, 20 are located in Nordenskiöld Land, three on Wedel Jarlsberg Land, and one each on James I Land and Dickson Land.

When looking further at the CH sites 100 m buffer overlapping RTS, reveals a total of 104 sites, with a significant proportion located in Wedel Jarlsberg Land (44 sites) and Nordenskiöld Land (43 sites). For the 6 m and 12 m buffers around the RTS, the number of sites rises to 106 for both values. Next are the safety zones, that intersect 42 zones, predominantly located in Wedel Jarlsberg Land (22 zones), followed by Nordenskiöld Land (6 zones) and James I Land (5 zones). For the 6 m and 12 m buffers around the RTS, the number of zones increases to 43 for both values. For priority sites, the analysis yielded the same 12 sites for all the three analyses. The majority of the priority sites are located in Nordenskiöld Land (5 sites, as follows: Russekeila – site no. 61 – Fig. 4a, Kokerineset – site no. 63, Barentsburg – site no. 65 – Fig. 4b, Colesbukta – site no. 67, Sveagruba – site no. 73 – Fig. 4f) and Dickson Land (3 sites, as follows: Pyramiden – site no. 64, Skansbukta – site no. 62, Svenskhuset – site no. 50). Of these, Russekeila has received the most attention in recent years, with comprehensive hazard assessments conducted on all the permafrost-related geohazards (Nicu et al., 2021; Rubensdotter et al., 2025) and detailed geophysical surveys (Tavakoli et al., 2023). This example could be replicated for other priority sites at the Archipelago scale.

The hazard assessment analysis highlights the CH sites from Nordenskiöld Land as a direct high-hazard hotspot from RTS (Fig. 3, lower left image), while Wedel Jarlsberg Land emerges as a secondary hazard

Fig. 2. Detail on the number of CH sites on Svalbard (by region) and the CH sites approached in this study (in green).

area. The *CH sites 100 m buffer* analysis demonstrates that Wedel Jarlsberg Land exceeds Nordenskiöld Land. Consequently, while Nordenskiöld Land exhibits the highest degree of direct RTS overlap, Wedel Jarlsberg Land CH sites are subject to increased proximity-based threats. This finding is consistent with earlier research that has highlighted the region's high density of both CH sites and RTS activity. This is due to the region's ice-rich permafrost, its historical settlement patterns, and its proximity to the coast (Nicu et al., 2021). *Safety zones* are at the highest risk in Wedel Jarlsberg Land, while *priority sites* are at the highest risk in Nordenskiöld Land, thus emphasising the necessity for targeted monitoring and intervention in these areas. This indicates that, while direct impacts are currently limited, a much larger number of CH sites are at risk from future expansion of RTS, especially as warming accelerates permafrost thaw.

3.3. CH hazard assessment to TEG

Several CH hazard assessments for gully erosion have been conducted in various regions worldwide (Kincey et al., 2017). However, there is only one study (Nicu et al., 2022) for their high-latitude counterparts – TEG, focused on Nordenskiöld Land, Svalbard. TEG can have negative effects on different types of immovable CH sites, including the destruction of archaeological deposits (loss of stratigraphy, removal of artifacts, exposure and fragmentation), disturbance of site integrity (relocation of buried materials, mixing of artifacts from different time periods, disturbing their original context), and various challenges for archaeologists (difficulty of excavation). TEG that forms beneath or alongside structures (buildings) lead to their tilting or collapses. Archaeological remains and artifacts buried in ice-rich soils are carried away by gully runoff. The formation of new drainage networks (especially along the cracks of ice-wedge polygons) can isolate sites, making them inaccessible to scientists and site managers, or prone to further erosion. One of the most exposed heritage elements are the organic artifacts (wood, textiles, bones) as they decay rapidly once exposed by the erosion process.

The study area was further examined to determine the number of *CH sites* that overlap a TEG (Fig. 3, upper image). The analysis revealed 4 sites, 3 of which are located in Nordenskiöld Land and one in Wedel Jarlsberg Land. For the 20 m and 30 m buffers around the TEG, the number of sites rises to 27 and 39, respectively. Of the 27 sites, 20 are located in Nordenskiöld Land, three in Bunsow Land, and two in Wedel Jarlsberg Land and Nathorst Land. Of the 39 sites, 29 are located in Nordenskiöld Land, 5 in Wedel Jarlsberg Land, three in Bunsow Land, and two are in Nathorst Land.

Looking at the *CH sites 100 m buffer* analysis overlapping TEGs reveals 113 sites, with a significant proportion located in Nordenskiöld Land (73 sites) and Wedel Jarlsberg Land (24 sites), followed by Dickson Land (7 sites), Bunsow Land (4 sites), Nathorst Land (2 sites), and Andree Land, Sabine Land, and James I Land (each with one site). For the 20 m and 30 m buffers around the TEG, the number of sites rises to 139 and 159, respectively. Of particular concern is the increase observed in Nordenskiöld Land, where values of 95 and 105 CH sites are deemed to be at risk for the two buffer values of 20 m and 30 m, respectively.

Regarding the *safety zones*, they intersect 63 zones, the majority of which are located in Nordenskiöld Land (33 zones), followed by Wedel Jarlsberg Land (15 zones) and James I Land (5 zones). For the 20 m and 30 m buffers around the TEGs, the number of zones increases to 71 and 75, respectively. Once more, the greatest increase is observed in Nordenskiöld Land, where 38 and 40 CH sites are at risk for the two buffer values.

For *priority sites*, the analysis identified 12 sites that intersect all the TEGs. Half of the priority sites are located in Nordenskiöld Land (6 sites), as follows: Barentsburg – site no. 65 – Fig. 4b, Tyske flyvrak i Adventaldalen og Hiorthhamn – site no. 54 – Fig. 4c, d, Longyearbyen gruveby – site no. 53 – Fig. 4e, Slettneset, Van Muydenbukta – site no. 70, Colesbukta – site no. 67, and Sveagruga – site no. 73 – Fig. 4f) and Dickson Land (4 sites, as follows: Pyramiden – site no. 64, Skansbukta – site no. 62, Svenskhuset – site no. 50, and Kapp Wijk – site no. 50). As for the buffers, only one site adds to the 12, which is located on Sabine Land (Dunér – site no. 74). Of these sites, Longyearbyen gruveby, Sveagruga,

Fig. 3. Quantitative charts of the hazard assessment of CH sites (upper central chart) for RTS (lower left) and TEG (lower right).

and Barentsburg are the most studied over the last years, with tangential connections regarding the TEGs affecting large parts of the sites (Nicu et al., 2022).

Same as in the case of RTS, Nordenskiöld Land is the region most affected. The increase in the number of sites affected is consistent across all the buffer distances, safety zones and priority sites (Fig. 3, lower right image). This is followed by Wedel Jarlsberg Land, Bünsow Land, Dickson Land, and Nathorst Land.

Both hazards are accelerating with climate change, and their spatial spread means that a much larger number of CH sites could be at risk soon. The buffer analysis value(s) approach is critical for proactive management, as many CH sites currently outside direct impact zones may soon be threatened by expanding of RTS and TEGs.

4. Discussion

4.1. Limitations and uncertainties

This study is fundamentally based on the best available datasets of RTS and TEG, providing near pan-Svalbard coverage of permafrost-related hazards (Nicu et al., 2024). However, the reliability of hazard

assessment is inherently limited by the spatial and temporal constraints of these inventories. Orthophotos from 2009 to 2011 are still the most recent reference for mapping, resulting in a static view of dynamic processes that are speeding up under increased Arctic warming. The lack of current imagery and long-term monitoring reduces the ability to detect recent changes and predict future hazard locations more accurately.

Due to the lack of long-term monitoring data from Svalbard, this study relies on erosion rates and HRR derived from Arctic analogues such as the Canadian and Russian High Arctic. While methodologically justified in data-scarce contexts, this introduces uncertainty due to site-specific differences in slope steepness, ground ice content, sediment structure, and local climate variables. The HRR values used (6 m yr^{-1} and 12 m yr^{-1} for RTS; 20 m yr^{-1} and 30 m yr^{-1} for TEG) are intended to capture median to upper-bound scenarios but may still underestimate site-level risks due to these complex interacting factors. Although slope orientation and permafrost composition are known to influence hazard formation and progression, the current analysis could not incorporate these dimensions quantitatively due to the lack of consistent, high-resolution terrain or subsurface data. Furthermore, TEGs typically exhibit accelerated erosion during their initial decades of development,

Fig. 4. Overview photos of some priority sites at risk from both RTS and TEG. a. Drone image of Russekeila; b. Photo from Barentsburg; c. Photo of the German airplane remains from Adventdalen; d. Photo of the German airplane remains from Hiorthhamn; e. Photo of the Longyearbyen gruveby; f. Photo of CH remains from Svea.

which later stabilises. This temporal pattern was not explicitly accounted for due to limitations in data availability. Nevertheless, the adoption of hazard buffers offers a practical approach to capturing potential lateral and longitudinal expansion of TEGs, especially under extreme climatic conditions (Kokelj et al., 2023).

The buffer distances used in this study are conceptually grounded in observed geomorphological dynamics and the legislative framework for heritage protection. The 100 m buffer reflects the statutory protection zone defined by the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act; however, its dominant influence on overlap results may lead to an overestimation of risk for some sites and an underestimation for others. Since site-specific vulnerability data were unavailable, the buffer application remains generalised, introducing interpretive limitations. A formal sensitivity analysis of buffer size effects was not conducted due to dataset constraints. Future research could improve accuracy by employing dynamic buffer modelling informed by terrain metrics, hazard intensity, and site-level characteristics. A complementary approach by (Bekele and Sinityn, 2023) offers a flexible risk framework that enables users to adjust key assumptions—such as hazard frequency, funding, or mitigation capacity—to explore how these influence heritage loss outcomes. Integrating such scenario-based sensitivity tools into Arctic heritage planning could strengthen prioritisation and support more adaptive, risk-informed decision-making under uncertainty.

Previous studies have documented the progressive widening and

lengthening of TEGs over time, particularly in Nordenskiöld Land where most mapped features remain in immature stages (Nicu et al., 2022). From a CH perspective, many sites—especially those composed of wooden structures or shallow archaeological deposits—are extremely sensitive to even small-scale disturbances. These conditions necessitate a precautionary approach, where hazard buffers inform spatial prioritisation for site monitoring, stabilisation, or documentation efforts (Rubensdotter et al., 2025; Tavakoli et al., 2023). Buffer analyses thus offer critical foresight, allowing managers to anticipate likely future exposures and direct limited resources accordingly.

4.2. Management and monitoring implications

Svalbard's Environmental Protection Act mandates automatic preservation of all cultural traces predating 1946. While this legislative framework is among the most precautionary in the Arctic (Iversen, 2023), its undifferentiated scope presents practical limitations under mounting climate and anthropogenic pressures. As cryospheric hazards such as RTS and TEG intensify, and as tourism expands in frequency and reach, a universal protection model has become increasingly untenable. Norwegian authorities have therefore prioritised 99 CH sites of high historical and cultural value. However, conservation strategies within this subset vary considerably—from passive monitoring to active intervention—highlighting governance challenges in implementing risk-

based conservation (Fatorić and Daly, 2023; Nicu and Fatorić, 2023).

Findings from this study support a transition toward regional hazard-informed planning. In particular, Nordenskiöld Land stands out for its density of overlapping hazards and CH sites, including Longyearbyen, Barentsburg, and Hiorthhamn. Local assessments in sites like Russekeila and Hiorthhamn (Rubensdotter et al., 2025) illustrate how targeted diagnostics can guide decisions on stabilisation, excavation, or documentation. Adopting this model more broadly could enable strategic allocation of conservation resources and enhance the resilience of priority assets.

Site-specific mitigation measures—including slope reinforcement, drainage improvements, or selective relocation—must be supported by improved monitoring capacity. Technologies such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), LiDAR, and thermal sensors can facilitate the early detection of geomorphic instability while contributing to long-term data continuity. Embedding these techniques into regulatory and permitting processes would help shift heritage management from reactive to anticipatory modes. This study also contributes to broader efforts to monitor non-economic loss and damage (L&D) from climate change. When maintained as a dynamic dataset, the *SvalCryo* inventory can support longitudinal tracking of degradation, disappearance, or irreversible damage to Arctic CH sites. This capability is particularly relevant for addressing underrepresented dimensions of L&D in international adaptation frameworks (Ford et al., 2025).

Despite these potential tools, limited institutional capacity remains a key barrier. Although the previous heritage management plan (2013–2023) outlined emergency measures and documentation strategies, the absence of a successor plan weakens continuity. Moreover, overlapping responsibilities between the Governor of Svalbard and the Directorate for Cultural Heritage have not been fully integrated into a cohesive system for climate-informed decision-making. Advancing such integration is essential for embedding CH risks within Arctic governance and ensuring that spatial diagnostics are translated into targeted conservation action.

4.3. Summary of practical implications and recommendations

The integration of cryospheric hazard mapping with the spatial distribution of CH sites offers an essential foundation for improving cultural heritage management under climate change. The findings underscore the need for regionally differentiated strategies, stronger institutional coordination, and adaptive frameworks for risk mitigation. To support the application of these insights in practice, the following recommendations are proposed in Table 2.

Table 2
Practical Recommendations for Arctic Heritage Management in the Context of Permafrost-Driven Hazards.

Domain	Recommendation
Risk-Based Prioritisation	Integrate RTS/TEG hazard exposure into CH frameworks to distinguish between passive and active protection needs.
Monitoring Strategies	Establish long-term, site-specific monitoring using UAVs, LiDAR, and thermal sensors to detect early instability.
Data Integration	Embed <i>SvalCryo</i> and related hazard inventories into spatial planning systems and regulatory workflows.
Policy Reform	Review heritage legislation to enable site-level adaptation, including triage-based interventions.
Institutional Capacity	Strengthen coordination between cultural and environmental agencies to ensure continuity and responsiveness.
L&D Accounting	Use updated hazard and heritage data to support monitoring of cultural losses within climate adaptation frameworks.
Knowledge Co-Production	Foster Arctic-wide collaboration and knowledge exchange on climate-resilient CH practices.

5. Conclusions

A comprehensive hazard assessment of CH from RTS and TEG was conducted at Svalbard Archipelago-wide scale. The hazard assessment analysis indicates that, while the number of CH sites currently directly affected by RTS is relatively small, the potential for rapid expansion of the risk is high. Both RTS and TEG pose a significant threat to Svalbard's CH sites. However, it is crucial to note that TEGs, due to their greater frequency and spatial extent, have a more pronounced impact on a greater number of sites as buffer distances increase. Nordenskiöld Land has been identified as the region of particular concern regarding both RTS and TEGs, reflecting its high density of both hazards and CH sites. For TEGs, it accounts for most direct and buffer-based overlaps. Wedel Jarlsberg Land emerges as a secondary hotspot, particularly for RTSs within the 100 m buffer (44 sites, surpassing Nordenskiöld Land's 43 sites). Other regions such as Dickson Land, Bünsow Land, and Nathorst Land, demonstrate a moderate risk, albeit with a significantly lower number of affected sites. The number of safety zones and priority sites at risk increases significantly with buffer distance, thus highlighting the potential for future expansion of the hazard to affect sites that are currently unaffected. Most sites at risk are concentrated in Nordenskiöld Land and Dickson Land, with key sites such as Longyearbyen gruveby, Barentsburg, and Sveagruba repeatedly highlighted for both hazards. It is imperative that priority is given to proactive monitoring, the implementation of dynamic buffer zones, and targeted conservation efforts in the most vulnerable regions – Nordenskiöld Land and Wedel Jarlsberg Land, especially as climate change accelerates permafrost-related hazards in Svalbard and globally. While Nordenskiöld Land has the highest direct overlap of RTS, the CH sites of the Wedel Jarlsberg Land are exposed to higher threats due to proximity. The main limitation for refining models and reducing uncertainties in Svalbard is the absence of multi-year monitoring of these processes, primarily due to the lack of orthophotos more recent than those from 2009 to 2011. This study provides the first quantitative, near pan-Svalbard assessment of the intersection between permafrost-driven hazards (RTS and TEG) and CH sites, safety zones, and priority sites. It offers new, large-scale evidence of the multifaceted risks facing Arctic CH sites. The findings of this study serve to further advance the broader understanding by demonstrating how hazard overlap and risks expand with buffer distance; reinforcing the need for regionally and pan-Arctic targeted conservation responses, improved integration of climate risk data, and clearer strategies for managing inevitable heritage loss across Svalbard. This will directly inform adaptive management and policy responses for the safeguarding of CH sites in a rapidly warming Arctic.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ionut Cristi Nicu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paloma Guzman:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Cristian Constantin Stoleriu:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Perplexity and DeepL to improve the readability and English of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation funding under Grant Agreement No: 101095253, THE-TIDA project. And by the Norwegian Research Council [grant number 351961, SASCHA project, 2024], under the European Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI CH), JPI Climate and Belmont Forum. ICN was partly supported by the Fram Centre project PermaRICH (Advanced Mapping and Monitoring for Assessing Permafrost Thawing Risks for Modern Infrastructure and Cultural Heritage in Svalbard). Many thanks for the constructive comments from the editor and two anonymous reviewers.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Barth, S., Nitze, I., Juhls, B., Runge, A., Grosse, G., 2025. Rapid changes in retrogressive thaw slump dynamics in the Russian high Arctic based on very high-resolution remote sensing. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 52 (7). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024gl113022>.
- Bekele, Y., Sinityn, A.O., 2023. Risk Analysis of the Impact of Natural Hazards on Cultural Heritage. Development of a Risk Assessment Tool.
- Biesbroek, R., Mirbach, C., Sietsma, A., Garschagen, M., 2025. Assessment of existing datasets for tracking progress towards the Global Goal on Adaptation (and beyond). *Clim. Pol.* 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2025.2517644>.
- Bonini, J.E., Vieira, B.C., Corrêa, A.C.d.B., Soldati, M., 2023. Landslides and cultural heritage—a review. *Heritage* 6 (10), 6648–6668. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6100348>.
- Chen, Y., Cheng, X., Liu, A., Chen, Q., Wang, C., 2023. Tracking lake drainage events and drained lake basin vegetation dynamics across the Arctic. *Nat. Commun.* 14 (1), 7359. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43207-0>.
- Dahlke, S., Hughes, N.E., Wagner, P.M., Gerland, S., Wawrzyniak, T., Ivanov, B., Maturilli, M., 2020. The observed recent surface air temperature development across Svalbard and concurring footprints in local sea ice cover. *Int. J. Climatol.* 40 (12), 5246–5265. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.6517>.
- Fatorić, S., Daly, C., 2023. Towards a climate-smart cultural heritage management. *WIREs Clim. Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.855>.
- Flyen, A.-C., Thuestad, A.E., 2023. A review of fungal decay in historic wooden structures in polar regions. *Conserv. Manag. Archaeol. Sites* 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13505033.2022.2156145>.
- Ford, J.D., Biesbroek, R., Ford, L.B., et al., 2025. Recommendations for producing knowledge syntheses to inform climate change assessments. *Nat. Clim. Change* 15, 698–708. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02354-6>.
- Fortier, D., Allard, M., Shur, Y., 2007. Observation of rapid drainage system development by thermal erosion of ice wedges on Bylot Island, Canadian Arctic Archipelago. *Permafrost. Periglac. Process.* 18 (3), 229–243. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp.595>.
- Gerlach, J., Kinossian, N., 2016. Cultural landscape of the Arctic: 'recycling' of soviet imagery in the Russian settlement of Barentsburg, Svalbard (Norway). *Polar Geogr.* 39 (1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1088937x.2016.1151959>.
- Godin, E., Fortier, D., Burn, C.R., 2012. Geomorphology of a thermo-erosion gully, Bylot Island, Nunavut, Canada. *Can. J. Earth Sci.* 49 (8), 979–986. <https://doi.org/10.1139/e2012-015>.
- Hjort, Y., Streletskiy, D., Doré, G., Wu, Q., Bjella, K., Luoto, M., 2022. Impacts of permafrost degradation on infrastructure. *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* 3 (1), 24–38. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00247-8>.
- Hollesen, J., Matthiesen, H., Møller, A.B., Westergaard-Nielsen, A., Elberling, B., 2016. Climate change and the loss of organic archaeological deposits in the Arctic. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 28690. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep28690>.
- Iversen, L., 2023. A collective imagination of the future of Svalbard communities. In: Albert, M., Brode-Roger, D., Iversen, L. (Eds.), *Svalbard Imaginaries. Arctic Encounters*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43841-7_10.
- Jiao, Y., Zhao, D., Ding, Y., Liu, Y., Xu, Q., Qiu, Y., Liu, C., Liu, Z., Zha, Z., Li, R., 2019. Performance evaluation for four GIS-based models purposed to predict and map landslide susceptibility: a case study at a World Heritage site in Southwest China. *CATENA* 183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2019.104221>.
- Kim, J.W., Kim, H.G., 2021. Landslide susceptibility analysis by type of cultural heritage site using ensemble model: case study of the Chungcheong region of South Korea. *Sensors Mater.* 33 (11). <https://doi.org/10.18494/sam.2021.3593>.
- Kincey, M., Gerrard, C., Warburton, J., 2017. Quantifying erosion of 'at risk' archaeological sites using repeat terrestrial laser scanning. *J. Archaeol. Sci. Rep.* 12, 405–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2017.02.003>.
- Kizyakov, A.I., Wetterich, S., Günther, F., Opel, T., Jongejans, L.L., Courtin, J., Meyer, H., Shepelev, A.G., Syromyatnikov, I.I., Fedorov, A.N., Zimin, M.V., Grosse, G., 2023. Landforms and degradation pattern of the Batagay thaw slump, Northeastern Siberia. *Geomorphology* 420, 108501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2022.108501>.
- Kokelj, S.V., Gingras-Hill, T., Daly, S.V., Morse, P., Wolfe, S., Rudy, A.C.A., van der Sluijs, J., Weiss, N., O'Neill, B., Baltzer, J., Lantz, T.C., Gibson, C., Cazon, D., Fraser, R.H., Froese, D.G., Giff, G., Klengenber, C., Lamoureux, S.F., Quinton, W., Young, J., 2023. The Northwest Territories Thermokarst mapping collective: a northern-driven mapping collaborative toward understanding the effects of permafrost thaw. *Arctic Sci.* 9 (4), 886–918. <https://doi.org/10.1139/as-2023-0009>.
- Lacelle, D., Brooker, A., Fraser, R.H., Kokelj, S.V., 2015. Distribution and growth of thaw slumps in the Richardson Mountains–Peel Plateau region, northwestern Canada. *Geomorphology* 235, 40–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.01.024>.
- Liu, Y., Qiu, H., Kamp, U., Wang, N., Wang, J., Huang, C., Tang, B., 2024. Higher temperature sensitivity of retrogressive thaw slump activity in the Arctic compared to the Third Pole. *Sci. Total Environ.* 914, 170007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.170007>.
- Luo, J., Yu, F., Niu, F., Yao, M., Lin, Z., Liu, M., Yin, G., Gao, Z., 2024. Recent rapid initiation and growth of retrogressive thaw slumps in the Hoh Xil region of the Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau. *CATENA* 243, 108158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108158>.
- Nesterova, N., Leibman, M., Kizyakov, A., Lantuit, H., Tarasevich, I., Nitze, I., Veremeeva, A., Grosse, G., 2024. Review article: retrogressive thaw slump characteristics and terminology. *Cryosphere* 18 (10), 4787–4810. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-18-4787-2024>.
- Nicu, I.C., 2021. Is digital shoreline analysis system "fit" for gully erosion assessment? *CATENA* 203, 105307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2021.105307>.
- Nicu, I.C., Asăndulesei, A., 2018. GIS-based evaluation of diagnostic areas in landslide susceptibility analysis of Bahluiet River Basin (Moldavian Plateau, NE Romania). Are Neolithic sites in danger? *Geomorphology* 314, 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2018.04.010>.
- Nicu, I.C., Fatorić, S., 2023. Climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage in polar regions: a systematic bibliometric review. *WIREs Clim. Change* 14 (3), e822. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.822>.
- Nicu, I.C., Lombardo, L., Rubensdotter, L., 2021. Preliminary assessment of thaw slump hazard to Arctic cultural heritage in Nordenskiöld Land, Svalbard. *Landslides* 18 (8), 2935–2947. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-021-01684-8>.
- Nicu, I.C., Tanyas, H., Rubensdotter, L., Lombardo, L., 2022. A glimpse into the northernmost thermo-erosion gullies in Svalbard archipelago and their implications for Arctic cultural heritage. *CATENA* 212, 106105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106105>.
- Nicu, I.C., Elia, L., Rubensdotter, L., Tanyas, H., Lombardo, L., 2023. Multi-hazard susceptibility mapping of cryospheric hazards in a high-Arctic environment: Svalbard Archipelago. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 15, 447–464. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-447-2023>.
- Nicu, I.C., Rubensdotter, L., Tanyas, H., Lombardo, L., 2024. Near Pan-Svalbard permafrost cryospheric hazards inventory (SvalCryo). *Sci. Data* 11, 894. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03754-7>.
- Pederson, J.L., Petersen, P.A., Dierker, J.L., 2006. Gullying and erosion control at archaeological sites in Grand Canyon, Arizona. *Earth Surf. Process. Landforms* 31 (4), 507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.1286>.
- Rantanen, M., Karpechko, A.Y., Lipponen, A., Nordling, K., Hyvärinen, O., Ruosteenoja, K., Vihma, T., Laaksonen, A., 2022. The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 3, 168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>.
- Riksantikvaren, A. Norwegian Directorate for Cultural Heritage Management. Retrieved 10 April 2025 from. <https://www.riksantikvaren.no/veiledere/askeladden/>.
- Rubensdotter, L., Nicu, I.C., Stalsberg, K., 2025. Complex geohazards at a high priority Arctic cultural heritage site at Russekeila – Kapp Linné, Svalbard. *CATENA* 254, 108935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2025.108935>.
- Santos, F., Calle, N., Bonilla, S., Sarmiento, F., Herrnegger, M., 2023. Impacts of soil erosion and climate change on the built heritage of the Pambamarca Fortress Complex in northern Ecuador. *PLoS One* 18 (2), e0281869. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281869>.
- Sdao, F., Lioi, D.S., Pascale, S., Caniani, D., Mancini, I.M., 2013. Landslide susceptibility assessment by using a neuro-fuzzy model: a case study in the rupestrine heritage rich area of Matera. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 13 (2), 395–407. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-13-395-2013>.
- Security, N.M.o.J.a.P., 2024. Meld. St. 26 (2023–2024) Report to the Storting (White Paper). Svalbard. <https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/f8407df1f6a641fbae2ca00f4509a64e/en-gb/pdfs/stm202320240026000engpdfs.pdf>.
- Tavakoli, S., Nicu, I.C., Frauenfelder, R., Gilbert, G., 2023. First geophysical investigations to study a fragile Pomor cultural heritage site at Russekeila – Kapp Linné, Svalbard. *J. Cult. Herit.* 63, 187–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.08.005>.
- Thuestad, A.E., Tømmervik, H., Solbø, S.A., 2015. Assessing the impact of human activity on cultural heritage in Svalbard: a remote sensing study of London. *Polar J.* 5 (2), 428–445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2154896x.2015.1068536>.
- Tømmervik, H., Thuestad, A., Stien, J., Klemetsen Ateroberg, M., Bjerke, J.W., 2025. High-arctic cultural heritage environments are deteriorated by cruise tourism: a case study from Svalbard. *J. Land Use Sci.* 20 (1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1747423x.2025.2476948>.

- Walls, M., Hvidberg, M., Kleist, M., Knudsen, P., Mørch, P., Egede, P., Taylor, G., Phillips, N., Yamasaki, S., Watanabe, T., 2020. Hydrological instability and archaeological impact in Northwest Greenland: sudden mass movement events signal new concerns for circumpolar archaeology. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2020.106600>.
- Ward Jones, M.K., Pollard, W.H., Jones, B.M., 2019. Rapid initialization of retrogressive thaw slumps in the Canadian high Arctic and their response to climate and terrain factors. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14 (5). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab12fd>.
- Yang, Y., Rodenhizer, H., Rogers, B.M., Dean, J., Singh, R., Windholz, T., Poston, A., Potter, S., Zolkos, S., Fiske, G., Watts, J., Huang, L., Witharana, C., Nitze, I., Nesterova, N., Barth, S., Goose, G., Lantz, T., Runge, A., Natali, S., 2025. A collaborative and scalable geospatial data set for Arctic retrogressive thaw slumps with data standards. *Sci. Data* 12, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04372-7>.